

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAMME CODE: DDIA

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word for Mac)

THE ART, STYLE AND MECHANICS OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In this response paper, I intend to review my understanding of the course material provided for Period 1 of the course, ACA-401D, summarise key concepts learnt and make a conclusion of my understanding of the subject.

The coursework introduced doctoral students to the art, style and mechanics of international academic writing. Period 1 provided a foundational basis and clarified elemental matters relating to academic writing. The reading requirements covered nine chapters, relating to topics such as Essay Writing, Plagiarism, Literature Review, Different Style Guides and the Chicago Manual Style Crib Sheet.

The core reading material for the coursework was supplemented by additional material on how to write a response paper by Cleenewerck and Gulma (EUCLID 2020) and a video clip, facilitated Professor Cleenewerck, to help doctoral students format their academic papers using a word processing application.

In this response paper, I seek to demonstrate that I have obtained an understanding of the key foundational concepts necessary to develop additional skills to improve my academic writing.

2) KEY CONCEPTS

The course material covered nine chapters and topics. However, I have chosen to focus on five key concepts below, which, in my view, constitute the fulcra of expected knowledge for Period 1 of ACA-401D.

a) Essay Writing

According to the University of New South Wales, ‘the aim of an academic essay is to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence’ (EUCLID 2019, 1). This avowed purpose for academic essays, therefore requires that it should be approached purposefully and must follow some basic steps.

The University of New South Wales has underscored the key issues to be observed in academic essay writing; including proper planning before commencement, undertaking a thorough research of the subject, and organising the essay and its structure in a proper form. It is also important to make appropriate references for source material, to edit the final draft of the essay and ensure its timely submission as recommended by the University of New South Wales.

As a professional, I am often confronted with the need to craft and review several documents each day. However, with only an informal and intuitive approach, I usually spend an inordinate amount of time on such tasks as I feel my way through the process, with an eye on a final draft that makes for logical sequencing and easy reading. The reiteration of the need for a structure in academic writing is therefore welcome and reinforces clear advice for a formal structure in writing. The knowledge obtained in essay writing also provides some assurance that after almost 20 years, when I last engaged in academic writing, my transition to academic writing may be less challenging than originally anticipated.

b) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is an unethical practice. Plagiarism, which is ‘use of source material without giving credit to the author of that source information’ (EUCLID 2019, 4), has been the bane of many otherwise brilliant writings. I, therefore, share the view that in academic and professional writing, the sources of information should be duly acknowledged and properly cited.

The need to avoid plagiarism was mentioned in chapter two but highlighted throughout the coursework. Two major forms of citations, ‘in-text’ citation and references, were introduced in chapter two and further expatiated in several other chapters of the core course material. The format to follow in citing source information was exemplified. In respect of ‘in-text’ citations, the use of quotations and paraphrasing of the source information was amply demonstrated. In light of the pervasive nature of online sources of

information I am particularly grateful for the orientation that was provided for citing online works

The admonishment against plagiarism and the ways to avoid it is timely as I begin my doctoral writing journey. I have been reminded to adopt a meticulous approach to documenting every source information that I may come across in my reading and research.

c) Different Style Guides

There are different styles of writing and, as a result, it is imperative that academic writing conforms to a particular style guide to ensure consistency. While creative writers may eschew the use of a style guide, academic writers do not have such a luxury and must conform to a guide in style of writing to ensure consistency.

It is for this reason that style guides are necessary. The style guide is ‘a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent’ (EUCLID 2019, 24). Chapter five, outlined different style guides and introduced the EUCLID preferred style guide, the Chicago Rules (Turabian).

For writers from a background of British English, it is quite difficult adjusting to American English, especially because of the diffidence it engenders for already familiar words and usages. However, fortunately, this potential difficulty has been anticipated and the recommendation for the preferred Rule and standard, has embodied flexibility of choice, which is useful to students coming from all manner of backgrounds. The unintended consequences, if the recommended Rule were to be strictly carried through, would have created some difficulty for SBE doctoral students.

d) Seeming tension between Standard American English and Standard British English

The subtle but real tension between Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) in the domain of World English was unravelled in chapter 6. The dominance of SAE over SBE, in recent years was clearly explained. There are many factors that have contributed to such a dominance, especially the magnitude of higher education in the United State as against that of the United Kingdom, the size of the publishing industry in the United States, and reach and influence of United States-led mass media and technology across the globe (EUCLID 2019, 4).

The highlighted differences between the SAE and SBE was one of the most useful clarification for me. A key challenge for native speakers of SBE is that the pervasive influence of SAE creates difficulties in applying a consistent style. As a professional required to craft and review different documents on a daily basis, I am often confronted with both standards. Throughout my formative education, I had been trained in the application of SBE. However, with the advent of personal computers, the default mode for

word-processing applications and online resources are usually set to SAE, thus, creating situations where words that are auto-corrected create a new norm of spelling. The tension between the two standards has often led me to succumb to the dominant standard – SAE – and created, in some instances, a fluid situation where the two standards creep into my writings, even though such melange is inappropriate for academic writing.

e) Chicago Manual Style Crib Sheet

Dr. Abel Scribe avers that the Chicago style is ‘the style of formatting books and research papers documents in the *Chicago Manual of Style* (CMS), 2003 and Kate Turabian’s *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996’ (EUCLID 2019, 44).

The crib sheet addressed issues such as recommended dictionaries for doctoral students, the proper forms for abbreviations, acronyms, capitalisation, compound words, and page formats.

The crib sheet provides, for me, a useful and easy to use reference that can assist doctoral students to appreciate the *Chicago Manual Style*.

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I want to indicate how useful this coursework has been. Having completed my advanced degree over 20 years ago, I have, expectedly, lost a bit of the finesse required to write an academic paper. This course work has brought back into focus the rigour required for academic papers and further deepened my understanding in areas that I need to pay greater attention to in order to be successful at academic writing.

I have been particularly reminded to engage in adequate planning before commencing a paper, to research thoroughly the subject matter and to write with a structure in mind. I have also been reminded to avoid plagiarism and have been provided useful formats to cite information that may be obtained from a source and intended for use in my work. The differences between SAE and SBE has been forcefully brought home to me during this coursework and the tools provided by the CMS Crib Sheet is helpful in serving as a rudimentary reference point for checking against expected standards.

In terms of pedagogy, a number of concepts such as plagiarism and proper citation were systematically repeated in different forms in the course material in a manner that ensured that the concept was properly understood. In a few instances, however, examples used for differentiation were repeated word for word and this created some amount of confusion such as the following examples in Chapter 4, page 20:

Example 1: My favorite types of sandwiches are peanut butter and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef, and turkey club. (Formal way)

However, some writers find it acceptable to omit the comma before the conjunction.

Example 2: My favorite types of sandwiches are peanut butter and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef, and turkey club. (Modern way)

I, however, appreciate the EUCLID approach to its doctoral programme as it has laid bare the foundational pitfalls to avoid in a doctoral writing. I am confident that other progressive course works will deepen my understanding of the academic writing process and its international dimension.

REFERENCES

1. Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA- 401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
2. Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2020. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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